

Original Articles

Comprehensiveness of conservation of useful wild plants: An operational indicator for biodiversity and sustainable development targets

Colin K. Khoury^{a,b,*}, Daniel Amariles^a, Jonatan Stevens Soto^a, Maria Victoria Diaz^a, Steven Sotelo^a, Chrystian C. Sosa^{a,c}, Julian Ramírez-Villegas^{a,d}, Harold A. Achicanoy^a, Jorge Velásquez-Tibatá^{e,f}, Luigi Guarino^g, Blanca León^{h,i}, Carlos Navarro-Racines^{a,d}, Nora P. Castañeda-Álvarez^g, Hannes Dempewolf^g, John H. Wiersema^{j,k}, Andy Jarvis^{a,d}

^a International Center for Tropical Agriculture (CIAT), Km 17, Recta Cali-Palmira, Apartado Aéreo 6713, 763537 Cali, Colombia

^b United States Department of Agriculture, Agricultural Research Service, National Laboratory for Genetic Resources Preservation, 1111 South Mason Street, Fort Collins, CO 80521, USA

^c Genetics and Biotechnology Laboratory, Plant and AgriBioscience Research Centre (PABC), Ryan Institute, National University of Ireland Galway, University Road, Galway H91 REW4, Ireland

^d CGIAR Research Program on Climate Change, Agriculture and Food Security (CCAFS), Km 17, Recta Cali-Palmira, Apartado Aéreo 6713, 763537 Cali, Colombia

^e Instituto de Investigaciones Biológicas Alexander von Humboldt, Calle 28A #15-09, Bogotá, Colombia

^f The Nature Conservancy, NASCA Conservation Program, Calle 67 No. 7 - 94, Piso 3, Bogotá, Colombia

^g Global Crop Diversity Trust, Platz der Vereinten Nationen 7, 53113 Bonn, Germany

^h Museo de Historia Natural Universidad Nacional Mayor de San Marcos, Av. Arenales 1256, Apartado 14-0434, Lima-14, Peru

ⁱ Department of Geography and the Environment, The University of Texas at Austin, 305 E. 23rd Street, CLA Building, Main Office- CLA 3.306, Austin, TX 78712, USA

^j United States Department of Agriculture, Agricultural Research Service, National Germplasm Research Laboratory, Building 003, BARC-West, Beltsville, MD 20705-2350, USA

^k Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History, 10th St. & Constitution Ave. NW, Washington, D.C. 20560, USA

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ABSTRACT

Plants are essential sources of food, medicine, shelter, fuel, feed, and forage, and provide a wide range of additional ecosystem and cultural services to humanity. In recognition of the tremendous value of useful plants and of the increasing threats to their persistence, international agreements including the Convention on Biological Diversity, the Sustainable Development Goals, and the International Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture have created ambitious conservation targets which must be measured through quantitative indicators so as to facilitate the development and implementation of strategies aimed at safeguarding their genetic diversity. Gaps in the current list of functioning indicators for these targets suggest that the development of effective measurements of the state of conservation of the genetic diversity within useful plants is a major challenge. Here we present a gap analysis indicator methodology that provides a pragmatic estimate of the comprehensiveness of conservation of the genetic diversity within useful wild plants, both *ex situ* and *in situ*. The methodology compares the geographic and ecological variation evident from analyses of the 'site of collection' of samples of plant taxa that are safeguarded in genebanks and other living plant repositories, as well as the variation evident in the proportion of species' ranges inhabiting protected areas, against the full range of geographic and ecological variation in their native distributions. The methodology enables a prioritization of species for immediate conservation action, and, when measured periodically, can quantify progress toward comprehensive conservation of these plants at global, regional, and national scales, including determining when that goal has been reached. Assessing almost 7000 taxa with the "Comprehensiveness of conservation of useful wild plants" indicator, we find that they are currently highly under-conserved, with less than three out of every 100 taxa assessed as sufficiently conserved or of low priority for further conservation action (overall global indicator = 2.78). Indicator results at the national and regional scales as well as by species use type varied, although virtually all countries, regions, and use categories were found to require further conservation action, particularly with regard to *ex situ* conservation. The results as well as input data and method code are available for indicator reporting and for conservation prioritization setting.

* Corresponding author at: International Center for Tropical Agriculture (CIAT), Km 17, Recta Cali-Palmira, Apartado Aéreo 6713, 763537 Cali, Colombia.
E-mail address: ckhoury@cgiar.org (C.K. Khoury).

1. Introduction

Plants are essential sources of human food, condiment, medicine, shelter, fuel, feed, and forage for livestock, pollinators, and game, and provide a wide range of additional ecosystem and cultural services of value to humanity (Gascon et al., 2015; Wiersema and León, 2013; Willis 2017). Unfortunately, many useful plants are threatened by habitat destruction and degradation, invasive species, climate change, pollution, and over-harvesting (Brummitt et al., 2015; Jarvis et al., 2008b; Newbold et al., 2015; Ramirez-Villegas et al., 2012), and are poorly represented in *ex situ* conservation repositories (Castañeda-Álvarez et al., 2016; FAO, 2010; Khoury et al., 2010; León-Lobos et al., 2012).

International recognition of the tremendous value of useful plants and of the increasing threats to their persistence has led to urgent calls for the comprehensive protection of these species in the highest level global agreements on development, conservation, and agriculture. These include the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), Strategic Plan for Biodiversity 2011–2020, Aichi Biodiversity Target 13 (CBD, 2010a) and Global Strategy for Plant Conservation (GSPC) Target 9 (CBD, 2010b), United Nations Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 2.5 (United Nations, 2015), and Article 5 of the International Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture (ITPGRFA) (FAO, 2002). While many of the targets set forth in these agreements allowed for a decade or more to accomplish their aims, conservation of the genetic diversity within these plants was much more urgently prioritized (i.e., by 2020 within Aichi Target 13, the GCPC, and SDG 2.5).

To measure progress toward these targets at national and global scales, a range of indicators have been proposed, are under development, or have been deployed. For Aichi Target 13, for instance, indicators include the numbers of accessions conserved in genebanks, the levels of protection of species and habitats in the wild, IUCN Red Listing indices, and the degree of national implementation of the Global Plan of Action for Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture (CBD, 2018). While these are pragmatic and complementary, additional metrics are needed to cover all taxa of interest to the targets and, importantly, to provide a more direct measure of trends with regard to the conservation of genetic diversity.

Plant conservation indicators based directly on genetic diversity information have been proposed and explored (Fussi et al., 2016; Gaudal et al., 2014; Hoban et al., 2014; Bruford et al., 2017; Schmeller et al., 2018), but metrics covering a wide range of plants are not currently feasible due to the lack of genetic data (Balmford et al., 2005; Brown and Hodgkin 2015; McCouch et al., 2013). Extensive sampling, extraordinary increases in investments in genotyping and data analysis, and further development of assessment methods would be required to directly quantify the genetic diversity within useful plants as a group worldwide. While this may become feasible at a future time as relevant technologies become more powerful and cost-effective (McMahon et al., 2014), a practical methodology that estimates trends in the conservation of genetic diversity at the highest possible accuracy is urgently needed if progress toward the international targets is to be measured.

To be useful, such an indicator must be reportable in a simple format at relevant scales of time and space for decision-making, while also offering disaggregated information that can contribute to prioritizing species, populations, and geographic areas for conservation action. To be sustainably operational, the indicator should be based on well-curated, openly available data and on methodologies that can be efficiently applied to that data at regular intervals. Measured over time, the indicator should quantify progress toward the goal of comprehensive conservation, including determining when that goal is met. For Aichi Target 13, for instance, that is when “the genetic diversity of cultivated plants and farmed and domesticated animals and of wild relatives, including other socio-economically as well as culturally valuable species, is maintained, and strategies have been developed and implemented for minimizing genetic erosion and safeguarding their genetic diversity” (CBD, 2010a).

Here we propose the use of a gap analysis methodology to measure the conservation status of useful species relevant to Aichi 13, GSPC 9, SDG 2.5, and Article 5 of the ITPGRFA, with particular attention to inclusion of socioeconomically and culturally valuable wild plants. This approach builds on methods developed over the past decade to measure the *ex situ* conservation status of crop wild relatives (Castañeda-Álvarez et al., 2016; Khoury et al., 2015a,b; Ramirez-Villegas et al., 2010), utilizing openly accessible data and tools. Our methodology provides an approximation of the distribution of a species’ genetic diversity, using the extent of eco-geographic (i.e., geographic and ecological) variation in its native range as a proxy, which has been shown to be an effective surrogate (Hanson et al., 2017; Hoban et al., 2018). The eco-geographic variation evident from an analysis of the locations of the ‘site of collection’ of samples conserved in genebanks and other living plant repositories, and that evident in the species’ range distributed within protected natural areas, is then measured against the eco-geographic variation found within the species’ entire native range, providing an efficient estimation of the current degree of conservation of its genetic diversity. The species is then categorized with regard to priority for further conservation efforts, and scores for multiple taxa are combined to provide indicator metrics at national, regional, and global scales. Performed periodically, the “*Comprehensiveness of conservation of useful wild plants*” indicator can measure progress toward the international targets, including determining when these have been reached.

2. Methods

The proposed methodology measures the extent of conservation of useful wild plant species in genebanks and other *ex situ* living plant repositories as well as in protected areas, and then combines the species level results to create the “*Comprehensiveness of conservation of useful wild plants*” indicator at various scales. The methodology includes five main steps, explained in detail below: 1. creating a dynamic list of socioeconomically and culturally valuable species, 2. compiling and processing species’ occurrence data, 3. modeling of species’ potential distributions based on occurrence data and climatic and other eco-geographic covariates, 4. gap analysis, i.e., comparing existing germplasm collections and designated protected areas with species’ distribution models, and 5. calculating the indicator across species at national, regional, and global scales.

All code implemented in our analysis is available at: <https://github.com/CIAT-DAPA/UsefulPlants-Indicator>. Implementation followed the Automated Dataset Execution design pattern (Erl et al., 2016), in which the workflow was coordinated by coded instructions in the R statistical package (R Core Team, 2017) that call the components (data acquisition and processing, modeling, gap analysis, and indicator generation). The total workflow was comprised of 70.7% R code language, 22.8% Java, 3.8% JavaScript, 2.5% HTML, and 0.2% Batchfile.

2.1. Create a global list of socioeconomically and culturally valuable species

With the aim of compiling well curated and easily accessible taxonomic and use data on species of socioeconomic and cultural value, we reviewed major online databases, including the USDA-Agricultural Research Service GRIN-Global World Economic Plants (WEP) database (based on Wiersema and León [2013], continually updated online), Mansfeld’s World Database of Agricultural and Horticultural Crops (IPK Gatersleben, 2018), the PROTA4U webdatabase (Wageningen University and Stichting Wageningen Research, 2015), Duke Phytochemical and Ethnobotanical databases (USDA, 2017), the Harlan and de Wet Crop Wild Relative Inventory (Vincent et al., 2013), and *Plants for a Future* (2012). We also surveyed pertinent academic literature (e.g., Rodríguez-Arévalo et al. 2017; Small, 2013; Willis, 2017).

We ultimately selected WEP as the single species list we would use, as it was considered to be the most globally comprehensive, is openly available, and is continuously updated, containing all three most

important data needs for the global species list: species names (i.e., taxonomy), socioeconomic and cultural use and value information, and native distribution by country. We found that the majority of species found in the other online databases, many of which are no longer continuously updated, were included in WEP, providing confidence that reliance on this curated database would provide reasonably comprehensive coverage of pertinent plants globally in both present and future assessments. As of January 2018, the WEP contained 15,768 distinct species with associated use information, which we determined to be well over the manageable maximum number of taxa for which species distribution modeling and conservation analyses could be accurately and efficiently performed at regular intervals.

Given the large number of plant species that can be considered of socioeconomic or cultural value, we selected those plants listed in WEP with the uses that best aligned with our understanding of the intention of the wording of Aichi 13, GSPC 9, SDG 2.5, and Article 5 of the ITPGRFA (Table 1). We excluded from the analysis weeds, poisonous plants, and ornamentals, as well as plants listed only as having potential (rather than confirmed) utility as genetic resources. After further filtering to remove species that are strictly cultivated, we selected a total of 6941 distinct socioeconomically and culturally valuable wild plant species for the analysis, the majority of which have been attributed with more than one use (Table 1). We analyzed the coverage of the selected species across countries and found them to be fairly well distributed globally (Supplementary Fig. 1). These species are native to 220 countries and territories, with a minimum count of one in Andorra, Falkland Islands, Gibraltar, Kiribati, Niue, Palestinian Territory, St. Helena, Timor-Leste, and U.S. Minor Outlying Islands, a maximum of 642 in Turkey, and a median of 86 per country worldwide.

2.2. Compile and process reference and conservation repository occurrence data

With the aim of compiling continually updated and easily accessible reference and conservation repository data for the selected species, we surveyed online biodiversity and genebank databases with global scope that provide access to occurrence information. We gathered data from the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF, 2018a), the Genesys plant genetic resources portal (Global Crop Diversity Trust, 2018a), and the Global Crop Wild Relative Occurrence Database (Global Crop Diversity Trust, 2018b).

For each database, we standardized species names against the GBIF Backbone Taxonomy, using the GBIF Species Lookup Tool (GBIF, 2018c) and the GBIF Species API v1 (GBIF, 2018b). A 96.0% match was found between GBIF Backbone and WEP, and a 93.3% match was found between the Backbone and the combined Genesys and Global Crop Wild Relative Occurrence Databases.

In preparation for the gap analysis, we classified each occurrence record according to whether it would be used only as an input into the species distribution modeling (labeled H, as most of these records source from herbarium records), or whether it would also be considered a ‘site where collected’ location of an existing living plant conservation repository accession (labeled G, as most records source from genebanks). For GBIF, this classification was performed by filtering the “Basis of Record” field, assigning “living specimen” as G, with the other pertinent categories (observation, literature, preserved specimen, human observation, machine observation, material sample, and unknown) assigned as H. All records in Genesys were assigned G, and records from the Global Crop Wild Relative Database had already been categorized appropriately.

To further refine (i.e., “scrub”) the occurrence data in preparation for species distribution modeling, we removed any coordinates located in bodies of water, as well as those found outside the native range as defined by WEP. We also selected only those reference occurrences collected from 1950 to the present, to ensure that we based distribution modeling on relatively recent data and to align this occurrence

information with the time period of the climatic information used in the distribution modeling. A resulting total of 43,126,547 scrubbed occurrence records for the 6941 species were available for use in species distribution modeling and conservation analyses, including 636,442 G records and 42,490,105 H records.

2.3. Model species distributions

With the aim of creating a modeling methodology that could be efficiently applied to a large number of wild plant species, we reviewed and tested openly available eco-geographic input data, modeling algorithms, and model evaluation methods frequently used in species distribution modeling and conservation analyses. We chose the Maximum Entropy (MaxEnt) algorithm as a standard and very commonly used tool for species distribution modeling (Costa et al., 2010; Elith et al., 2006; Phillips and Dudik, 2008) and because of recent advances in making the algorithm’s underlying methodology openly accessible (Phillips et al., 2017). We ran the MaxEnt software in batch mode through the R statistical package *dismo* (Hijmans et al., 2017). MaxEnt requires three inputs to model the geographic distribution of a species: (i) presence observations, (ii) pseudo-absences, and (iii) eco-geographic predictors. We processed these as follows:

- (i) Presence observations: we used all spatially distinct coordinates in the occurrence datasets. For 1007 (14.5% of total) species with > 2100 occurrence records and for which preliminary modeling attempts failed due to the excess of occurrence information, we refined the quantity of records (to an average of 2021) to obtain a more manageable number for modeling efficiency. This subsampling was done through the function “nstrata” (SamplingUtil R package, available at <https://github.com/DFJL/SamplingUtil>) using a “proportional” method to maintain geographic extent and coverage.
- (ii) Pseudo-absences: Following Barbet-Massin et al. (2012), we defined the number of pseudo-absences according to the number of presences to avoid overfitting. For species with fewer than 50 presences, the number of pseudo-absences was 100 times the number of presences. For species with 50 or more presences, the number of pseudo-absences was 10 times the number of presences.
- (iii) Eco-geographic predictors: We chose the following eco-geographic data inputs based on their use in recent publications, ongoing curation, and global coverage: 19 bioclimatic variables, plus solar radiation, wind speed, and water vapor pressure, derived from WorldClim 2 (Fick and Hijmans, 2017), and altitude, from the CGIAR-CSI dataset based on the NASA Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (STRM) data (Jarvis et al., 2008a). We also included slope and aspect, calculated from the altitude dataset using the terrain

Table 1

Count of assessed taxa within each socioeconomic and culturally valuable use category selected from the World Economic Plants (WEP) database. Most species were attributed to more than one use category.

Use category	Number of taxa
Animal foods (<i>forage, fodder, etc.</i>)	764
Bee plants (<i>honey production</i>)	188
Environmental use plants (<i>agroforestry, erosion control, shade, etc.</i>)	2209
Food additives (<i>flavoring, coloring, emulsifier, etc.</i>)	379
Fuels (<i>fuelwood, charcoal, petroleum substitute, etc.</i>)	189
Genetic sources (<i>crop wild relatives- only species with recorded uses in crop breeding or close relatives to cultivated crops</i>)	1607
Human foods (<i>cereal, fruit, nut, etc.</i>)	1123
Materials (<i>essential oils, fiber, gums, etc.</i>)	2010
Medicines (<i>folklore, veterinary, etc.</i>)	2881
Pesticides (<i>disease vector control, plant pest control, etc.</i>)	41
Socially relevant plants (<i>hallucinogen, religious, stimulant, etc.</i>)	118
Total number of distinct species	6941

function in R package raster (Hijmans, 2017). All eco-geographic predictors were at a spatial resolution of 2.5 arc-minutes (approximately 5 km at the equator).

For each species, we calculated the modeled distribution as the mean of five MaxEnt model replicates ($K = 5$), using linear, quadratic, hinge and product features, with a regularization parameter $\beta = 1.0$. Following previous gap analysis studies (Khoury et al., 2015a,b; Ramirez-Villegas et al., 2010), we evaluated the MaxEnt model output using the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC), the standard deviation of the AUC across replicates (STAUC), the proportion of the potential distribution model with a standard deviation (of the $K = 5$ replicates) above 0.15 (ASD15), and the calibrated area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (cAUC). To be considered an accurate and stable model, all of the following must have been accomplished: an AUC mean $> = 0.7$; STAUC < 0.15 ; ASD15 $< = 10\%$; and cAUC $> = 0.4$.

In cases where a model did not meet the evaluation parameters, or when the total number of distinct coordinate records for a species was < 10 and thus considered insufficient for modeling (Castañeda-Álvarez et al., 2016), we created alternative potential distribution models by drawing a buffer of 0.5 degrees (approximately 50 km radius) around all occurrences. Species distributions models were thresholded using the maximum sum of sensitivity and specificity threshold (Liu et al., 2005, 2013) and then clipped to the extent of the native country boundaries as listed in WEP (Khoury et al., 2015a,b).

All modeling processes were written and run in R, using packages snowfall (Knaus, 2015), raster (Hijmans, 2017), maptools (Bivand and Lewin-Koh, 2017), rgdal (Bivand et al., 2018), rgeos (Bivand and Rundel, 2017), data.table (Dowle and Srinivasan, 2017), gtools (Warnes et al., 2015), velox (Hunziker, 2017), PresenceAbsence (Freeman and Moisen, 2008), rJava (Urbanek, 2017), dismo (Hijmans et al., 2017), tidyverse (Wickham, 2017), SDMTools (van Der Wal et al., 2014), rgeos (Bivand and Rundel, 2017), shapefiles (Stabler, 2013), sp (Pebesma and Bivand, 2005), and plyr (Wickham, 2011).

2.4. Gap analysis: estimate the degree of representation of species in conservation repositories (*ex situ*) and in protected areas (*in situ*)

2.4.1. *Ex situ* representativeness

This analysis estimates the degree of representation of species in living plant conservation repositories. Three scores are used: the Sampling Representativeness Score (SRS), the Geographical Representativeness Score (GRS_{ex}), and the Ecological Representativeness Score (ERS_{ex}). The three scores are averaged to provide a final *ex situ* conservation score (FCS_{ex}), building on the gap analysis methods described by Ramirez-Villegas et al. (2010), Khoury et al. (2015a,b), and Castañeda-Álvarez et al. (2016).

The SRS (Eq. (1)) provides a general indication of the completeness of genebank and other *ex situ* conservation collections, comparing the current total count of germplasm accessions (G) available in such repositories against the total count of reference (H) records, with an ideal (i.e., comprehensive) conservation ratio of 1:1. This simple score makes use of all compiled reference and germplasm records, regardless of whether they possess geographical coordinates, providing a general indication of species' representation *ex situ*, as the number of accessions sufficient to capture the genetic diversity of a species is correlated with the extent of its distribution (Hoban and Strand, 2015; Ramirez-Villegas et al., 2010).

$$SRS = \left[\frac{\text{number of G records}}{\text{number of H records}} \right] * 100 \quad (1)$$

SRS is bound between 0 and 100. In this and in the subsequent measurements, if no G or H records existed, species were automatically considered to be of high priority for further conservation action due to

the lack of information, and thus assigned a value of 0.

The GRS_{ex} (Eq. (2)) is a geographic measurement of the proportion of a species range that can be considered to be conserved in *ex situ* repositories. A comprehensive conservation under this metric is considered to have been accomplished only when germplasm samples have been collected across the entire geographic range. Buffers ("CA50") of 0.5 degrees (approximately 50 km radius) were created around each G collection point in order to estimate geographic areas already collected within the species' distribution models.

$$GRS_{ex} = \left[\frac{\text{total area (km}^2\text{) of CA50 of all G records}}{\text{total area (km}^2\text{) of species distribution model (SDM)}} \right] * 100 \quad (2)$$

The ERS_{ex} (Eq. (3)) is an ecological measurement of the proportion of a species range that can be considered to be conserved in *ex situ* repositories. The ERS_{ex} compares the eco-regional diversity encompassed in *ex situ* conservation repositories to the diversity throughout species' distribution models, considering comprehensive conservation to have been accomplished only when every eco-region potentially inhabited by a species is included at least once within the set of CA50 germplasm 'site where collected' locations. The layer used for estimating the ERS_{ex} contained 867 distinct terrestrial ecoregions (Olson et al., 2001) as a proxy for ecological and environmental diversity, following methods outlined in Khoury et al. (2015a,b) and Castañeda-Álvarez et al. (2016).

$$ERS_{ex} = \left[\frac{\text{number of ecoregions represented within CA50 of G records}}{\text{number of ecoregions represented within SDM}} \right] * 100 \quad (3)$$

A Final *ex situ* Conservation Score (FCS_{ex}) (Eq. (4)) was computed by calculating the mean of the three *ex situ* conservation metrics.

$$FCS_{ex} = \left[\frac{SRS + GRS_{ex} + ERS_{ex}}{3} \right] \quad (4)$$

2.4.2. *In situ* representativeness

This analysis measures the extent of species' representation within protected areas. We used the World Database of Protected Areas (WDPA) (IUCN, 2014), selecting terrestrial and coastal reserves marked as designated, inscribed, or established. Two scores are used: the Geographical Representativeness Score (GRS_{in}) and the Ecological Representativeness Score (ERS_{in}), which are averaged to provide a final *in situ* conservation score (FCS_{in}).

The GRS_{in} (Eq. (5)) is a geographic measurement of the proportion of a species range that can be considered to be conserved in protected areas. The GRS_{in} compares the area (km^2) of species' distribution models located within (i.e., geographically overlapping with) protected areas versus the total area of species' distribution models, considering comprehensive conservation to have been accomplished only when the entire distribution occurs within protected areas.

$$GRS_{in} = \left[\frac{\text{area (km}^2\text{) of SDM located within protected areas}}{\text{total area (km}^2\text{) of SDM}} \right] * 100 \quad (5)$$

The ERS_{in} (Eq. (6)) is an ecological measurement of the proportion of a species range that can be considered to be conserved in protected areas. The ERS_{in} compares the ecological variation encompassed within species' ranges located inside protected areas to the ecological variation encompassed within the total area of species' distribution models, considering comprehensive conservation to have been accomplished only when every ecoregion potentially inhabited by a species is included within the distribution of the species located within a protected area.

$$ERS_{in} = \left[\frac{\# \text{ of ecoregions represented in SDM located in protected areas}}{\text{number of ecoregions represented within SDM}} \right] * 100 \quad (6)$$

A Final *in situ* Conservation Score (FCS_{in}) (Eq. (7)) was computed by calculating the mean of the two *in situ* conservation metrics.

$$FCS_{in} = \left[\frac{GRS_{in} + ERS_{in}}{2} \right] \quad (7)$$

2.4.3. Combined score

A Final combined Conservation Score (FCS_{c-mean}) was calculated for each species by averaging its FCS_{ex} and FCS_{in} (Eq. (8)). As additional useful metrics, we computed a minimum combined score (FCS_{c-min}) by selecting whichever score (between the FCS_{ex} and FCS_{in}) was smaller, reflecting the stance that both conservation strategies are important and both need to be increased to an ideal level. We also calculated a maximum combined score (FCS_{c-max}) by selecting whichever score was greater, reflecting the stance that the total comprehensiveness of conservation is what is ultimately important, regardless of the conservation strategy used. In analyzing the results, we found the use of the FCS_{c-min} for indicator calculation to provide such low scores per country and globally that the indicator was essentially not useful, at least at this present time. Similarly, we found the FCS_{c-max} to produce indicator results that we determined to be overly optimistic with regard to the conservation status of these species at national and global levels, per our experience. The FCS_{c-mean} was thus the score used in the indicator calculation, described further below.

$$FCS_{c-mean} = \left[\frac{FCS_{ex} + FCS_{in}}{2} \right] \quad (8)$$

2.4.4. Conservation priority categories

Species were categorized based on their conservation score, which fit in a numeric range between 0 and 100: High priority for further conservation for species where $FCS < 25$; medium priority where $25 \leq FCS < 50$; low priority where $50 \leq FCS < 75$; and sufficiently conserved for taxa whose $FCS \geq 75$.

2.5. Calculate indicator

We considered comprehensive conservation for a species to have occurred when its FCS_{c-mean} was ≥ 50 on the 0–100 scale, i.e., when that the species was determined as sufficiently conserved or of low priority for further conservation action. We calculated the “Comprehensiveness of conservation of useful wild plants” indicator based on the proportion of species assessed as comprehensively conserved (Eq. (9)).

$$\text{Indicator} = \left[\frac{(\text{number of species whose } FCS_{c-mean} \text{ is } \geq 50)}{\text{Total number of species}} \right] * 100 \quad (9)$$

The indicator was also calculated separately with regard to *ex situ*, and with regard to *in situ* conservation, by calculating the proportion of species sufficiently conserved or of low priority for further conservation action for each particular conservation strategy. The indicator was calculated at national and regional levels by assessing only those species listed as native to that country or region, as given in WEP. Regional classifications were aligned to the standard country or area codes for statistical use (M49 code) (International Organization on Standardization, 2006; United Nations Statistics Division, 2012).

3. Results

Of 6941 socioeconomic and culturally valuable wild plant species included in the analysis, we were successful in generating validated species distribution models for 4362 (62.8%), with CA50 buffer potential distributions created for the 1555 (22.4%) taxa that failed to

pass the model validation step and the 710 (10.2%) species with fewer than 10 distinct occurrence points (see Supplementary Fig. 2 for a richness map combining these models). A total of 6627 (95.5%) taxa were thus included in the full gap analysis. Another 183 (2.6% of total) species had occurrences but no coordinate data, and nine (0.1%) had coordinates but only outside their native ranges. In both of these cases only the Sampling Representativeness Score (SRS) was calculated, with the other metrics assigned 0s. We were unable to find occurrence data for the remaining 122 (1.8%) species; these were assigned scores of 0 for all metrics (Supplementary Table 1).

An example of spatial results for a wild coffee species, *Coffea liberica* W. Bull ex Hiern, is provided in Fig. 1. The potential distribution model of the species is shown in Fig. 1A. The taxon is native to West, Central, and East Africa and is used directly by consumers as a beverage base and stimulant, as well as by coffee breeders as a source of disease resistance. The locations where the species has been previously collected for *ex situ* conservation, surrounded by the CA50 buffer, are shown in Fig. 1B, and the overlap of the model with existing protected areas is displayed in Fig. 1C. For this species, which had 53 germplasm samples (15 with coordinate information) and 459 herbarium samples (205 with coordinates), SRS was calculated at 11.6, GRS_{ex} at 2.6 (Fig. 1B), and ERS_{ex} at 22.6, producing an FCS_{ex} of 12.3 on a scale of 0 to 100. With regard to *in situ* conservation, GRS_{in} was calculated at 14.5 (Fig. 1C) and the ERS_{in} at 90.3, producing an FCS_{in} of 52.4. The final combined conservation score (FCS_{c-mean}) for the species was thus 32.3, categorizing it as of medium priority for further conservation action. As with this example species, conservation gaps for the great majority of assessed taxa were particularly severe with regard to geographic representation, and much less so with regard to ecological variation. Likewise, conservation *ex situ* tended to be much less comprehensive than conservation in protected areas.

The global indicator of the “Comprehensiveness of conservation of useful wild plants” was calculated at 3.3 with regard to the state of *ex situ* conservation and 40.7 with regard to protection *in situ*, with a combined conservation indicator of 2.8 on the scale from 0 to 100 (Fig. 2, Supplementary Table 2). Note that the combined global indicator is calculated from the already averaged conservation scores per species (i.e., FCS_{c-mean}), and therefore is not the simple mean of the global *ex situ* and *in situ* scores. With regard to the combined indicator, 3,017 (43.5%) species were assessed as high priority for conservation action, 3,731 (53.8%) as medium priority, 185 (2.7%) as low priority, and 8 (0.1%) as sufficiently conserved.

Although all socioeconomic and cultural use categories were found to be substantially under-conserved, the categories varied in degree, with genetic sources (i.e., crop wild relatives), animal foods, and human foods being somewhat better conserved overall. Conversely, socially relevant plants, pesticides, medicines, materials, fuels, environmental use plants, and food additives were found to be the least well conserved (Fig. 3, Supplementary Table 2). Conservation *in situ* for all utilization categories was found to be much more substantial than conservation *ex situ*.

Comprehensiveness of conservation varied among countries and regions, although all countries and regions were assessed to be significantly under-conserved, with the highest combined conservation scores still reaching only 7.1 for the Republic of Korea, 5.3 for Botswana, and 5.3 for Chile (Fig. 4, Supplementary Fig. 3 and Table 2, online interactive at <https://ciat.cgiar.org/usefulplants-indicator/>). While countries with extremely low conservation as well as others with somewhat higher levels were distributed in all world regions, country scores did cluster by continent, particularly with regard to the *in situ* indicator, with countries in Europe and the Americas having relatively higher scores. The combined indicator was weakly correlated with species richness per country ($\rho = 0.49$, P-value = 0.0009) (Supplementary Fig. 4). The number of species that had no coordinate information, or no data at all and thus could not be assessed fully also varied among countries, with up to 118 species (6.1% of national total)

Fig. 1. (A) Potential distribution model for *Coffea liberica* W. Bull ex Hiern based on occurrence locations. The lighter colored background displays the native country boundary used to clip the model; (B) *ex situ* ‘site where collected’ locations surrounded by a ca. 50 km buffer (in red), over the potential distribution model, used to calculate the GRS_{ex} . The buffered areas are considered to be sufficiently collected in the geographic sense, whereas the non-buffered (i.e., green-colored) areas of the potential distribution are considered to be geographic gaps in *ex situ* conservation; (C) Potential distribution occurring within and outside of designated protected areas, used to calculate the GRS_{in} . Areas of potential distribution of the species located outside of protected areas are considered to be geographic gaps in *in situ* conservation. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

in China, 61 (4.7%) in India, and 34 (4.1%) in Indonesia. In no country did more than 10% of species lack these data. This said, the future generation and publication of reference and conservation repository information on such species, as well as those currently offering limited coordinate data, would represent important steps in improving the ability of the indicator to assess the full range of useful wild plants.

4. Discussion

4.1. Toward the international biodiversity conservation and sustainable development targets

Here we report that less than three out of every 100 useful wild species assessed worldwide are sufficiently conserved or of low priority for further conservation action (overall $FCS_{c-mean} = 2.8$). The evident gaps in conservation of these useful wild plants *ex situ* parallels the results of analyses focused on crop wild relatives (Castañeda-Álvarez et al., 2016; FAO, 2010; Khoury et al., 2010) and are particularly worrying in comparison to the representation of the assessed taxa within protected areas. While part of this poor state of *ex situ* conservation in comparison to *in situ* may be attributed to a lack of availability of occurrence information (including coordinates) from *ex situ* repositories that harbor such species but are not currently connected to online databases, it remains highly likely that the great majority of useful wild plants, and particularly those not directly utilized as food or as genetic resources for agricultural crops, are only marginally conserved *ex situ*. Urgent efforts to increase the representation of these

species in *ex situ* conservation repositories are thus warranted, particularly given findings that biodiversity loss in natural habitats does not yet appear to be slowing (Butchart et al., 2010; Willis, 2017) and that shifting species ranges due to climate change is likely to impact the efficacy of existing protected areas (Beaumont et al., 2011; Pecl et al., 2017; Williams et al., 2007).

Because wild plants provide a wide range of essential ecosystem and cultural services, including aiding in the mitigation of climate change impacts (Gascon et al. 2015; Wiersema and León, 2013), and because the *ex situ* conservation of sufficient genetic diversity within some (mainly tropical) plants can be quite difficult and expensive (León-Lobos et al., 2012), the enhancement of protection of these useful wild plants in their natural habitats is also well justified. To more sufficiently conserve these species *in situ*, the protected areas network will need greater investment and, possibly, expansion (Brooks et al., 2006; Le Saout et al., 2013; Meilleur and Hodgkin, 2004; Newbold et al., 2015; Dinerstein et al., 2017). As *in situ* conservation actions advance, particular attention will need to be paid to ensuring the protection of highly threatened species (Venter et al., 2014), stemming ongoing habitat destruction within and on the edges of protected areas (Laurance et al., 2012), and modifying protected areas as species’ ranges shift due to climate change (Hampe and Petit, 2005).

4.2. Usefulness and limitations of the indicator

The global indicator method described here provides a balance of accuracy and efficiency, modeling at relatively high spatial resolution

Fig. 2. Proportion of species in each conservation priority category at the global scale (total species $N = 6941$), measured with regard to *ex situ* conservation, *in situ* conservation, and as the combined (FCS_{c-mean}) metric. An interactive version is available at <https://ciat.cgiar.org/usefulplants-indicator/>.

Fig. 3. Proportion of species in each conservation priority category per socioeconomic and cultural use category, measured with regard to *ex situ* conservation, *in situ* conservation, and as the combined (FCS_{c-mean}) metric. The total number of species assessed per category is provided in Table 1. An interactive version is available at <https://ciat.cgiar.org/usefulplants-indicator/>.

almost 7000 species with a reasonable use of computational resources. The results provide indicator metrics aggregated at global, regional, country, and use category levels, as well as species-specific scores and maps. The indicator is based on continually updated and openly available data and tools to enable its sustainability over time and its adaptability for other research purposes. Our indicator represents a more direct and integrative approach to estimate the state of conservation of genetic diversity than do those providing static counts of accessions held in genebanks, or those simply categorizing threats to species and their habitats. Therefore, it could serve as a useful complement to existing and proposed indicators for Aichi 13, GSPC 9, SDG 2.5, and Article 5 of the ITPGRFA.

While the indicator is robust in that it uses well-established taxonomic, occurrence, and eco-geographic information as inputs, and employs popular open-source software, a number of vulnerabilities of the method should be mentioned. First, the quality of the results is highly dependent on the comprehensiveness and the degree of ongoing curation of the data and technologies used. Taxonomic and geographic errors and gaps have been recognized in resources such as GBIF (Anderson et al., 2016; Belbin et al., 2013; Gajji et al., 2013; Yesson et al., 2007) and Genesys (Guzzon and Ardenghi, 2017), and the magnitude of these errors are such that significant further investments will be needed before such databases achieve a high level of accuracy and global coverage. Importantly, our proposed methodology can contribute to the identification of these deficiencies, highlighting taxa

for which species distributions models are not possible due to lack of data or to poor data quality, potentially aiding in the prioritization of further work to generate or improve occurrence data.

Reporting of *ex situ* conservation holdings, including ‘site where collected’ coordinates, within easily accessible online databases such as Genesys and GBIF, is certainly insufficient with regard to the totality of samples safeguarded in genebanks, botanic gardens and other living plant conservation repositories around the world, and may contribute to an overestimation of gaps in *ex situ* conservation for some useful wild plant species. Some information on these holdings likely exists in additional, scattered online databases or in off-line datasets, while other conservation repositories may not yet have digitized their data. Including this information in a global indicator that must be regularly calculated presents a considerable challenge, but is a necessary step toward fully assessing the *ex situ* representation of useful wild plants. The incorporation of such datasets into Genesys, GBIF, or other easily accessible databases would enable their inclusion in this indicator.

Our method includes the generation of geographical predictions of the ecological niche of species based on the statistical relationship between reference sightings and eco-geographic information. Although species may potentially inhabit these niches, environmental factors acting at finer scales (e.g., soil types), dispersal limitations, and direct impacts on species populations (e.g., habitat destruction or modification) also determine species’ ranges (Newbold et al., 2015; Ramirez-Villegas et al., 2012; Soberón and Nakamura, 2009). The improvement

Fig. 4. Indicator results per country a) combined (FCS_{c-mean}) conservation indicator, b) *ex situ* conservation indicator, c) *in situ* conservation indicator. Red indicates a low level of conservation/ low indicator values/ high priority for further conservation action. Interactive versions of these maps are available at <https://ciat.cgiar.org/usefulplants-indicator/>.

of distribution models taking such factors into account is also a considerable challenge due to the lack of comprehensive global datasets on these drivers as well as of methodologies enabling the efficient prediction of their impacts on different species.

In order to be applicable to all species mentioned in the international biodiversity and sustainable development targets, our approach will need to be expanded to include domesticated plants and livestock. The challenges in applying the method to these species include patchy occurrence data and the limited development of distribution modeling methods for species whose ranges are determined more by cultural and socioeconomic factors than by environmental and geographic drivers. Particularly for animals, baseline data on the number and distribution of species, breeds, and functional populations is critically needed before more refined analyses can be developed (FAO, 2015; McGowan et al., 2018; Redford and Dudley 2018).

Provided that further progress can be made on resolving these data and methodological gaps, the method proposed here has potential to offer a useful indication of the comprehensiveness of conservation across all “cultivated plants and farmed and domesticated animals and wild relatives, including other socio-economically as well as culturally valuable species” (CBD, 2010a). As genetic data across the ranges of these taxa becomes more available, the method can also be adapted to incorporate that information to enable a more direct analysis of the state of conservation of species’ genetic diversity.

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Declarations of interest

None.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2018.11.016>.

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